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Research Article

**A PROSPECTIVE RESEARCH TO ASSESS
POSTOPERATIVE ARRHYTHMIAS AMONG PATIENTS
UNDERWENT PEDIATRIC CARDIAC SURGERY****¹Dr Muhammad Nouman Butt, ²Dr Saba Asif, ³Dr. Aniqua Rehman**¹Medical Officer, Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Hospital , Gujrat²Services Hospital Lahore³Jinnah Medical and Dental College**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of this study was to determine risks, onset and treatment for early postoperative arrhythmias among patients who underwent pediatric cardiac surgery. The primary focus of the study was to gauge results by uniform therapies along with analysis of issues faced by children who were operated at an earlier and later age.

Patients & Methods: This prospective study was carried out on a total of 224 consecutive pediatric patients who underwent cardiac surgery at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (February 2019 to January 2020). In the course of study, a total of 24 patients were excluded as they were treated without cardiopulmonary bypass.

Results: Median age of the study population was 24 months (50.1 ± 62.4). The age range for the selected sample was (0.5 to 216 months). Arrhythmia developed among 15 patients (7.5%); most repeated arrhythmia was junctional ectopic tachycardia observed among 7 patients (46.6%) and supraventricular tachycardia observed among 5 patients (33.3%). The occurrence of all junctional ectopic tachycardias happened in the first 24 hours of ICU admission. Five patients responded to conventional management protocols out of seven; whereas, two still required amiodarone infusion. Non-arrhythmias patients required less cardiopulmonary bypass time; whereas, arrhythmias patients required significantly longer duration.

Conclusion: Children presented very low arrhythmias onset after open-heart surgery for junctional ectopic tachycardia. There was no significant predictor than a significant longer duration for cardiopulmonary bypass. Multiple factors attribute to arrhythmias following pediatric cardiac surgery and more research work on large scale samples is required to unfold more about the matter.

Keywords: Cardiac, Heart Defects, Arrhythmias, Congenital, Tachycardia and Postoperative Complications.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Muhammad Nouman Butt,**

Medical Officer, Aziz Bhatti Shaheed Hospital, Gujrat

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INTRODUCTION:

Congenital heart disease repair associated mortality and morbidity has dramatically reduced with the introduction of improved cardiac surgical protocols. Most of the immediate complication can be managed. Postoperative arrhythmia has grabbed attention in last few years as it is repeatedly reported in early postoperative duration after congenital cardiac surgery [1 – 3]. Most of the cases are manageable at an early stage. Although numerous studies focused on the issue, no guidelines are available about vexing issues. Particularly, junctional ectopic tachycardia (JET) is notorious due to associated mortality rates and prolonged ICU stay. Various studies have targeted the possibilities and surgical approaches to assess the management, risks and incidence of arrhythmias [4 – 7]. Acute postoperative arrhythmia is reported about (7.3% to 48%) [4 – 7]. Early postoperative arrhythmias' pathophysiological causes include cannulation, myocardial incision, sutures adjacent to conduction system, and acute intracardiac pressure changes attributed to pressure and volume overload [1 – 10]. Moreover, other related onsets include cardiopulmonary bypass with ischemia-reperfusion, electrolyte shifts, cellular biochemical effects and catecholamine administration affect cellular membrane stability and its outcome is increased myocardial automaticity and irritability [11, 12]. The objective of this study was to determine risks, onset and treatment for early postoperative arrhythmias among patients who underwent pediatric cardiac surgery. The primary focus of the study was to gauge results by uniform therapies along with analysis of issues faced by children who were operated at an earlier and later age.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This prospective study was carried out on a total of 224 consecutive pediatric patients who underwent cardiac surgery at Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (February 2019 to January 2020). In the course of study, a total of 24 patients were excluded as they were treated without cardiopulmonary bypass. Enrolled patients were under the age of eighteen years and they were managed with one dedicated surgical team. Ethical committee approved our research protocols. Parents also gave informed consent for inclusion of their children in the research study. We did not include all those patients who were having postoperative arrhythmia and operated without CPB. Another 24 were excluded in the course of research as their procedures were also carried out without CPB. Study included 66% male and 34% female patients who underwent cardiac surgery at moderate hypothermic CPB (28 to 32) °C with or without aortic cross-clamp. del Nido cardioplegia single dose was given after aorta cross-clamping. Six or twelve lead ECG was attempted in the cardiothoracic ICU as permitted available tubes

placement. Eighteen hours ICU hospitalization was a must to go for early postoperative arrhythmias evaluation. Diagnosis was also confirmed through temporary atrial pacing wires if deemed necessary. As sinus tachycardia is notorious arrhythmia detection confounders; therefore, all neonates underwent careful ECG recordings. All patients were also observed for sustained hemodynamic instability ECG at blood pressure (<50 mm) and (<40 mm) respectively for infants and neonates. We included sustained (above 30 s) arrhythmias, classified as supraventricular tachycardia – non-JET, JET, atrial flutter, high-grade atrioventricular block, ventricular fibrillation and ventricular tachycardia. Every possible option was exercised to remove the chances of sinus tachycardia and sinus bradycardia. Standard definitions applied for arrhythmias identification [13]. Supraventricular tachycardia included atrioventricular nodal reentrant tachycardia, ectopic atrial tachycardia, inappropriate sinus tachycardia and atrioventricular reentrant tachycardia. More than one per minute beats were premature ventricular or supraventricular. Metabolic and electrolyte disturbances are arrhythmia reversible causes which were observed and corrected. JET was treated by avoiding hyperthermia, pain control, limiting exogenous catecholamines and optimizing sedation. While observing the permission of ventricular rate, synchrony restoration was made through atrial overdrive pacing with the help of temporary atrial wires. In case of rapid ventricular rate and effective overdrive pacing, amiodarone infusion was additionally administered with already mentioned protocols. Amiodarone (5ml) was given as an initial intravenous dose per kilogram for two hours and (10 to 15 ml) per kg/day. Dose was adjusted as required. Patients with junctional escape rhythm or atrioventricular block were paced with the help of temporary pacing wires. Persistent high-grade atrioventricular block was treated with permanent pacing.

We also documented detailed data about patients regarding their demographics, preoperative treatment, complete cardiac diagnosis, intraoperative parameters (aortic cross-clamp time, CPB time, total surgery time), operative procedure and postoperative parameters (oxygen saturation, electrolyte levels, blood pH, sodium, serum calcium and potassium levels along with the requirement of inotropic agents). Level of serum creatine kinase MB and other medications were also documented. We analyzed the research outcomes on SPSS software (P-Value < 0.05).

RESULTS:

Median age of the study population was 24 months (50.1±62.4). The age range for the selected sample was (0.5 to 216 months). Arrhythmia developed

among 15 patients (7.5%); most repeated arrhythmia was junctional ectopic tachycardia observed among 7 patients (46.6%) and supraventricular tachycardia observed among 5 patients (33.3%). The occurrence of all junctional ectopic tachycardias happened in the first 24 hours of ICU admission. Five patients responded to conventional management protocols

out of seven; whereas, two still required amiodarone infusion. Non-arrhythmias patients required less cardiopulmonary bypass time; whereas, arrhythmias patients required significantly longer duration. Detailed outcomes analysis has been made in the given tabular and graphical presentation.

Table – I: Age Stratification

Age	Patients
<1 Month	1
1 - 12 Months	77
13 - 72 Months	87
73 - 144 Months	11
144 - 216 Months	24

Table – II: Patients' Characteristics

Variable	Unit	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum
Weight	kg	14.7±14.6	10	0.26	85
Body surface area	m ²	0.58±0.38	0.48	0.1	2
SpO ₂	-	93.8%±7.3%	99%	66	100%
Aortic cross clamp time	min	51.4±22.5	47	8	126
Cardiopulmonary bypass time		82.3±37.6	72	15	240
Temperature during surgery		30.8C±2.3C	32C	18C	34C
Surgery duration	h	3.4±0.9	3	2	9
Serum creatinine	g dL ¹	0.5±0.21	0.45	0.2	1.2
Serum albumin		3.1±0.2	3	2.9	3.3
Intensive care unit stay	h	64.8±48	48	18	312

Table – III: Type and Incidence of Cardiac Arrhythmia

	Disease	Patients (200)	Arrhythmia (15)
Acyanotic congenital heart disease	ASD+PS+hypertrophic cardiomyopathy	1	1 (ventricular ectopics)
	ASD	26	1 (sinus bradycardia)
	VSD	75	2 (JET)
	Interrupted aortic arch	1	1 (SVT)
	Anomalous left coronary artery from pulmonary artery	1	1 (SVT)
	Subaortic membrane	2	-
	Atrioventricular defect	1	-
Cyanotic congenital heart disease	Tetralogy of Fallot	42	3 (JET)
	Tetralogy of Fallot with absent pulmonary valve	1	-
	DORV+VSD+PS	9	1 (JET)
	DORV+atrioventricular septal defect+PS	2	1 (ventricular bigemini)
	DORV+VSD without pulmonary stenosis	3	-
	VSD+PS	5	1 (JET)
	ASD+PS	2	-
	Total anomalous pulmonary venous connection	4	1 (SVT)
	TGA with intact ventricular septum	13	1 (SVT)
	TGA+VSD	8	1 (SVT)
	TGA with atrioventricular septal defects	1	-
	TGA+VSD+PS	1	-
	Tricuspid atresia+VSD+PS+restrictive ASD	2	-

Table – IV: Patient's Characteristics (Arrhythmia)

Diagnosis	Arrhythmia Type	Age (Months)	Cross clamp Time (min)	CPB Time (min)	ICU Stay (hrs)	CK-MB (UL-1)	Arrhythmia Duration (hrs)	Treatment	Outcome
ASD, pulmonary stenosis, hypertrophic cardiomyopathy	Ventricular ectopic	204	38	104	50	40	Persisted	Oral Beta Blocker	Continued
Sinus Venosus ASD	Sinus bradycardia	192	74	120	24	48	48	None	Recovered
VSD	JET	9	73	100	96	85	48	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic, amiodarone	Recovered
VSD, left vena cava	JET	6	47	83	72	69	28	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
VSD, pulmonary stenosis	JET	60	40	60	72		24	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Tetralogy of Fallot	JET	24	33	57	120	63	56	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Tetralogy of Fallot	JET	24	52	73	120	52	48	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Tetralogy of Fallot	JET	36	48	108	144	82	96	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic, amiodarone	Expired
Interrupted aortic arch	SVT	8	101	150	312	59	72	Withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Anomalous left coronary artery from pulmonary artery	SVT	4	60	138	260	87	72	Withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Total anomalous pulmonary venous connection	SVT	4	50	80	96	86	72	Withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Transposition of great vessels + VSD	SVT	2	86	133	240	86	84	Withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Transposition of great vessels + ASD	SVT	2	100	240	170	87	72	Withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Double outlet right ventricle + VSD + pulmonary stenosis	JET	9	62	117	144	44	60	Surface cooling, withdrawal of inotropic	Recovered
Double outlet right ventricle + ASD + pulmonary stenosis	Ventricular bigemini	36	38	64	120	48	48	None	Recovered

Table – V: Postoperative Arrhythmias Risk Factors

Variable	Unit	Arrhythmia (15)		No Arrhythmia (185)		P-Value
		Value	Range	Value	Range	
Age	month	41.9±65.4	2-204	50.7±62.2	0.5-216	0.6
Body surface area	m ²	0.48±0.38	.1-1.5	0.59±0.38	.2-2	0.25
SpO ₂		90.9%±8.5%	78%-100%	94.1%±7.19%	66%-100%	0.1
Aortic cross clamp time	min	62.2±21.42	33-101	50.6±22.43	8-126	0.54
Cardiopulmonary bypass time		108.5±46.7	57-240	79.99±36.5	15-240	<0.05
Temperature during surgery		30C±3.8C	18C-32C	30.9C±2.2C	18C-34C	0.16
Creatine kinase	U L ¹	1327±760.1	557-3850	1138.9±571.8	104-3850	0.23
Creatine kinase-MB		65.9±17.3	40-87	69.7±15.6	38-96	0.36
pH		7.4±0.1	7.3-7.45	7.4±0.01	7.28-7.5	0.9
HCO ₃	mmol L ¹	23.1±2.01	19-26	23.7±1.6	18-26.1	0.17
Sodium	mEq L ¹	141.1±3.3	135-145	140.1±3.7	129.148	0.3
Potassium		3.4±0.3	3.2-4.1	3.3±0.5	1-4.1	0.57
Calcium	mg dL ¹	0.9±0.2	.8-1.4	1±0.2	.7-1.4	0.36
Intensive care unit stay	h	134.4±80.5	24-312	59.2±39.7	18-240	<0.001

DISCUSSION:

Although many improvements have been made in the outcomes of pediatric cardiac surgery arrhythmia is still a major factor contributing to mortality and morbidity rates [1]. Various postoperative pediatric cardiac surgery arrhythmia types are about 48% [2 – 4]. We reported arrhythmia about 7.5% which is less than reported other studies [2 – 4, 8, 9]. Young aged patients are at an increased risk of postoperative pediatric cardiac surgery arrhythmias. Higher mean age is a reason behind low onset of said incidence in this research. Our dedicated team, uniform protocol, cardioplegia and surgical techniques may also have reduced arrhythmia. Our definition of arrhythmia may also attribute in its reduced incidence (sustained for more than 30 s) [8, 9].

Most common arrhythmia was JET also observed in other series [2 – 4]. All JET diagnosed patients had a ventricular septal defect either with cardiac malformation or in isolation. In our setting, JET genesis may attribute to tricuspid annulus traction which is needed for ventricular septal defect exposure. However, our incidence was less than others, it can be explained due to negligible allowed traction on tricuspid annulus and judicious use of stay sutures to achieve cardiac exposure as found in other series [2, 6]. Past studies show a relation of JET with anomalous pulmonary vein drainage surgery or great vessels transposition, but not in our case [2].

Literature describes associated risks as younger age, longer aortic cross-clamp duration, prolonged CPB duration, deep hypothermic circulatory arrest, cyanosis and type of surgery [2 – 4, 7, 8]. We reported that prolonged CPB duration has an association with higher arrhythmia incidence which has also been previously reported [2 – 4]. Explanations to CPB as a causative agent include inflammatory markers production altering ischemia reperfusion injury, myocardial membrane potential, histamine release [12, 13]. Arrhythmia has no significant relation with aortic cross clamp time which is in contradiction to previous studies [2 – 4, 5]. Myocardial damage also develops arrhythmia due to injuries like free radical-mediated or ischemia reperfusion [11]. Our patients did not show a significant increase in serum creatine kinase MB which refers to better myocardial protection may be attributed to administering of del Nido cardioplegia. Adult patients also enjoy the advantages of del Nido cardioplegia [12].

CONCLUSION:

The outcomes conclude that prolonged ICU stay attributes to early postoperative arrhythmias. The onset of arrhythmias is significantly low in this study in comparison to other series. Multiple factors attribute in the lower onset of arrhythmia incidences such as experienced surgeons, cardioplegia type, operative protocols and postoperative protocols. Further studies on large samples will help to explore

more. Only one out of six deaths can be attributed to arrhythmias which shows that it is manageable.

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